

Does the participation of the diaspora make scientific collaborations different? An investigation on co-authorship with the Brazilian scientific diaspora in COVID-19 research

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Abstract

Studies have pointed out that although international collaboration is fundamental to research, relationships between Global North and South researchers are often asymmetrical. In the last decade, interest has grown in the role of scientific diasporas, especially in promoting more balanced interactions between researchers from the global North and South. However, empirical studies still need to be carried out to explore this hypothesis. The objective of this work was to investigate whether the participation of the scientific diaspora with researchers from their country of origin alters scientific production in terms of inclusion into international research networks, research topics, and the impact of publications. We carried out a comparative bibliometric study based on two samples of articles in international collaboration (with and without collaboration with the Brazilian scientific diaspora). The analysis corpus comprises 60 scientific articles about COVID-19, indexed in the OpenAlex database, between 2020 and 2022. The results showed that the sample of articles with diaspora involved a more significant number of institutions and authors and achieved a more substantial impact.

1. Introduction

Collaborative efforts are increasingly becoming crucial for advancing knowledge and for facing and solving complex problems in various scientific fields. The search for answers usually requires inter- or multidisciplinary approaches, depending on the joint work of researchers with different backgrounds and scientific perspectives (Prabhune, 2023; Bennett & Gadlin, 2012).” The more diverse the teams, the greater the chances of finding solutions to global problems,

such as pandemics and contemporary social and geopolitical challenges. Furthermore, collaborations become increasingly essential (Nature, 2021).

The importance of collaboration became even more evident with the COVID-19 pandemic, whose multidimensional impacts did not respect territorial or disciplinary boundaries. Hazelton (2021, unpag.) states: “If the pandemic has taught us anything, it’s the importance of scientific collaboration.” Furthermore, the more complex investigations become, the more “collaborations across organizational, disciplinary, and cultural boundaries extend the possibilities of discovery” (Dusdal & Powell, 2021, p. 235).

However, as the literature points out, relations between Global North and South scientists are surrounded by asymmetries, as more horizontal relations generally occur between scientists from central countries. On the other hand, relationships with scientists from peripheral or semi-peripheral countries tend to be subordinated to research agendas and rules defined by scientists from the Global North (Olechnicka et al., 2019; Feld & Kremer, 2019).

In the last decades, there has been more interest in the role of scientific diasporas. According to Kuznetsov (2013), diaspora are populations abroad that share a national, civic, or ethnic identity with a particular homeland. In this work, diaspora refers to highly qualified emigrants who work in the scientific, technical/technological, and innovation fields, according to the definition presented by Ho et al. (2015).

Scholars are exploring whether members of these diasporas in the Global North can act as bridges, helping to facilitate the international inclusion of researchers from the Global South. The scientific diaspora can be essential in international collaborations, promoting more balanced interactions between Global North and South researchers. Therefore, studies on diaspora collaboration with their peers in their homeland become essential sources of evidence for a better understanding of patterns of scientific collaboration. However, further empirical studies are still needed to explore and confirm this hypothesis fully. These results can also guide public policies that foster partnerships with the diaspora.

This article compares international collaboration between Brazilian researchers abroad (scientific diaspora) and international collaboration with partners of other nationalities. Our research question is: Do diaspora members in the Global North act as bridges for researchers from the Global South? This work aimed to investigate whether the participation of the scientific diaspora with researchers from their country of origin alters scientific production in terms of inclusion into international research networks, research topics, and the impact of publications. To this end, we carried out a bibliometric study to analyze the similarities and differences in research topics (concepts), institutions, authors, and collaboration patterns during the COVID-19 pandemic, comparing articles with and without diaspora authors. We also developed a methodology that can be applied in the future to analyze larger samples.

2. Material and Methods

The research is exploratory with a quantitative approach (Figure 1). We adopted bibliometric procedures for data collection, organization, and analysis. A bibliometric analysis was developed using the OpenAlex database to identify scientific articles about COVID-19 published between 2020 and 2022. This search resulted in 17,409 papers authored by

individuals affiliated with Brazilian institutions. Of this total, 5,659 (32.3%) were conducted in international co-authorship.

Figure 1 – Stages of the Methodology

We used a multimethod approach to identify Brazilian authors affiliated with institutions outside Brazil. First, we analyzed the authors' institutional affiliations across all their articles in the OpenAlex database to determine if they were previously affiliated with a Brazilian institution and later with institutions abroad. Next, we checked if they had a CV on the Brazilian Lattes Platform¹. After triangulating data from both sources, we identified 755 articles likely involving members of the Brazilian diaspora. Then, we selected a subsample of 130 high-visibility articles (citations and altmetrics). Finally, after manually verifying the nationality of all the authors, we chose 60 articles for our analysis. Of these, 30 were co-authored with members of the Brazilian scientific diaspora, and 30 were not.

We utilized indicators related to institutions, authors and collaboration and an indicator of concepts². Scientific collaboration identification was performed using the network analysis method (Maia & Caregnato, 2008). The quadratic co-authorship matrices, generated in Python, were exported to Microsoft Excel software and subsequently imported into UCInet 6 software, which allowed for the extraction of network author degree, centrality, and intermediation coefficients (O'Malley; Marsden, 2008; Zhang; Luo, 2017). For the graphical representation, we used the VOSViewer software.

For the categorization of concepts, we employed Zipf's Law (Zipf, 1949), which measures the frequency of words in regions of concentration (core, interesting, and noise) within a thematic or disciplinary field of science. The results were graphically presented using Microsoft Excel and WordClouds (wordclouds.com).

¹ A governmental database containing researchers CVs, widely used in Brazil for research and academic evaluation.

² The OpenAlex database structures its research topics, referred to as 'concepts', into six hierarchical levels, containing approximately 65,000 indexed concepts. Each article can be classified into multiple concepts based on its title and abstract, using an automated classifier trained on the Microsoft Academic Graph corpus.

3. Results

The analysis of the articles with diaspora members identified 1,059 authors, with publication variation ranging from 1 to 6 articles (an average of 1.19 articles per author). In the sample of articles without diaspora members, 497 authors were identified, with publications ranging from 1 to 5 articles (an average of 1.08).

The distribution of articles with diaspora members shows that 1,049 (99%) authors published between 1 and 3 articles. Thus, ten authors stand out as the most productive in the sample, with variations between 4 and 6 occurrences. In the sample of articles without diaspora members, similarities in distribution were observed, with 99% of authors having between 1 and 3 articles and only three authors with 5 and 4 occurrences, respectively. In this scenario, it is observed that both samples of articles have few authors with greater productive representation. However, the sample of articles with diaspora members has more productive authors.

The sample with diaspora members had authors filiated to 462 institutions, while another 218 institutions were identified in articles from the sample without diaspora members. However, the production of articles on COVID-19 is concentrated in a few institutions in both samples (Table 1).³

Table 1 - Main institutions in the sample of articles with and without diaspora members

WITH DIASPORA			WITHOUT DIASPORA		
Institution	Occurrence	%	Institution	Occurrence	%
UNIVERSIDADE DE SAO PAULO	176	13,84	UNIVERSIDADE DE SAO PAULO	33	6,04
UNIVERSITY OF OXFORD	90	7,08	INSTITUTE FOR HEALTH METRICS AND EVALUATION	31	5,68
YALE UNIVERSITY	48	3,77	COLUMBIA UNIVERSITY	26	4,76
UNIVERSITY OF GLASGOW	38	2,99	FUNDACAO DE MEDICINA TROPICAL	23	4,21
IMPERIAL COLLEGE LONDON	26	2,04	UNIVERSIDADE FEDERAL DO RIO DE JANEIRO	22	4,03
FUNDACAO OSWALDO CRUZ	25	1,97	UNIVERSITY OF GENOA	20	3,66
UNIVERSIDADE FEDERAL DE PELOTAS	21	1,65	UNIVERSIDADE FEDERAL DE MINAS GERAIS	19	3,48
HEALTH AND EDUCATION RESEARCH MANAGEMENT AND EPIDEMIOLOGIC SERVICES	18	1,42	UNIVERSIDADE ESTADUAL DE CAMPINAS (UNICAMP)	17	3,11
HOSPITAL ISRAELITA ALBERT EINSTEIN	17	1,34	WACOL, QLD, AUSTRALIA	16	2,93
WORLD HEALTH ORGANIZATION PAKISTAN	15	1,18	UNIVERSITY OF WASHINGTON	15	2,75
NATIONAL INSTITUTES OF HEALTH	14	1,10	UNIVERSIDADE FEDERAL DE SERGIPE	12	2,20
CLINICAL RESEARCH INSTITUTE	13	1,02	FUNDACAO OSWALDO CRUZ	10	1,83
FUNDACAO HOSPITALAR DE HEMATOLOGIA E HEMOTERAPIA DO AMAZONAS	12	0,94	UNIVERSITY OF CINCINNATI	8	1,47
UNIVERSIDADE FEDERAL DE SAO PAULO	11	0,86	UNIVERSITY OF LONDON	7	1,28
UNIVERSITY OF EDINBURGH	11	0,86	UNIVERSITY OF PADUA	7	1,28
UNIVERSITY OF SFAX	9	0,71	IMPERIAL COLLEGE LONDON	6	1,10
CARDIFF UNIVERSITY	8	0,63	CINCINNATI CHILDREN S HOSPITAL MEDICAL CENTER	5	0,92
HOSPITAL SIRIO LIBANES	8	0,63	UNIVERSIDADE FEDERAL DE SAO PAULO	5	0,92
UNIVERSIDADE FEDERAL DO RIO DE JANEIRO	8	0,63	UNIVERSITY OF SPLIT	5	0,92
HARVARD UNIVERSITY	8	0,63			
DUKE UNIVERSITY	8	0,63			
KEELE UNIVERSITY	7	0,55			
JOHN RADCLIFFE HOSPITAL	7	0,55			
UNIVERSITY OF CAMBRIDGE	6	0,47			
DIAMOND LIGHT SOURCE	5	0,39			
ROYAL VETERINARY COLLEGE	5	0,39			
CDL LABORATORIO SANTOS E VIDAL	5	0,39			
UNIVERSITY OF KWAZULU NATAL	5	0,39			
INSTITUTE FOR APPLIED ECONOMIC RESEARCH	5	0,39			
FUNDACAO GETULIO VARGAS	5	0,39			
UNIVERSITY OF LIVERPOOL	5	0,39			
SECRETARIA MUNICIPAL DE SAUDE BELO HORIZONTE	5	0,39			

The University of São Paulo is the prominent Brazilian institution in the sample with diaspora members (14% of occurrences) and the sample without diaspora members (6%). Brazilian institutions notably collaborate with the University of Oxford, Yale University, University of Glasgow, and Imperial College London (15% of total authors) in the sample with diaspora members. In the sample without diaspora members, the following institutions stand out: Institute for Health Metrics and Evaluation, Columbia University, University of Genoa, Wacol, University of Washington, University of Cincinnati, University of London, University of Padua, Cincinnati Children's Hospital Medical Center, and University of Split, representing approximately 25% of the total author occurrences.

³ The institutions were counted based on author affiliation. As in some articles there is more than one author per institution, the occurrence numbers exceed the number of articles in both samples.

Based on the observation of the institution lists from both samples, we notice two differences: the list of institutions with five or more occurrences in the sample with diaspora members includes a higher total number of institutions (32 vs. 19), and more institutions located outside of Brazil (63% vs. 52%).

The analysis of scientific collaboration in the samples with and without diaspora members reveals low network density (*With Diaspora* = 0.102; *Without Diaspora* = 0.080), centrality (*With Diaspora* = 2.561%; *Without Diaspora* = 1.881%), and network intermediary centrality (*With Diaspora* = 12.71%; *Without Diaspora* = 0.94%). These low indices were expected because the bibliometric study sought articles on COVID-19 without defining a specific area. Therefore, the authors were not necessarily expected to collaborate among them. Despite the absolute numbers, we observe that the density, centrality, and betweenness centrality of the diaspora member article sample (*With Diaspora*) are higher than the sample without members.

This analysis is supported by observing authors with the highest centrality among all articles in each sample. Only ten authors with the highest intermediary centrality were identified in both samples. These authors have published articles co-authored with other authors. Among the 1,059 (*With Diaspora*) and 497 authors (*Without Diaspora*), they are the intermediary authors within and between network groups. Therefore, they are the authors connecting the network (Figure 2).

Figure 2 - Co-authorship network of the sample of articles without diaspora (A) and with diaspora members (B), 2020-2022, OpenAlex

The co-authorship network of the sample of articles with diaspora members (Figure 2 B) allows for the interpretation of a diverse network composed of 3 clusters: *blue* (comprising two foreigners), *green* (comprising three foreigners and one Brazilian researcher in Brazil – Paola Cristina Resende), and *red* (comprising three Brazilian researchers in Brazil and one diaspora member – Renato D. Lopes). At the forefront of collaboration between the red group and other clusters lies the Brazilian researcher José Luiz Proença Modena. However, it is worth noting that the red cluster only has one collaboration among its members, which sets it apart from the blue and green clusters. Notably, Andrew Rambaut and Oliver G. Pybus, foreign authors of the green cluster, exhibit a higher degree of centrality and intensity of scientific interaction, thus enhancing communication and cooperation among members and clusters.

Figure 6 - Distribution of citations and altmetrics of articles published by authors affiliated with institutions in Brazil in international co-authorship with and without diaspora members on COVID-19, 2020-2022, OpenAlex

4. Discussion and Final Considerations

We investigated the effects of the Brazilian scientific diaspora through a concrete case study focused on COVID-19 research. We addressed how the diaspora can contribute to more equal relationships between Global North and South researchers. This topic is becoming increasingly relevant as understandings grow about the importance of international mobility and global knowledge networks for individuals, organizations, and countries, as well as for the advancement of science.

The findings suggest that articles involving diaspora members tend to include more institutions in Brazil and abroad and larger research teams exploring a broader range of topics. The data indicates that scientific collaboration, influence, and the facilitation of communication on COVID-19 are somewhat more intense when diaspora members are involved. These indicators suggest that the scientific diaspora helps create more integrated networks, significantly contributing to the international visibility of scientists from the Global South. Moreover, the data reinforces that scientific collaboration, influence, and communication regarding COVID-19 are more robust when diaspora members are involved. In contrast, the study indicates that authors from the subset without diaspora members are more likely to engage in networks predominantly composed of local or national researchers, even when participating in international collaborations.

The results highlight the importance of public policies that strengthen international collaboration networks involving the diaspora, particularly by directing interventions toward those members of the diaspora who are already mobilized, willing, and able to contribute.

Another contribution of this study is the methodology developed. The methodology employed is robust, leveraging OpenAlex to effectively focus on COVID-19 papers and compare collaborations involving diaspora members versus those that do not. The approach taken to address the problem is novel, particularly in developing a methodology using an automated pipeline that scales to larger datasets.

However, we emphasize that the results discussed in this work cannot be generalized, as the bibliometric indicators selected for analysis are derived from two small samples. Although we used similar selection and analysis criteria, the sample sizes may introduce biases.

A new research agenda to follow up on this study is to qualitatively characterize the relationship with the Brazilian scientific diaspora using other instruments, such as interviews.

Open science practices

The content generated during the research is stored in the Unicamp Research Data Open Repository (REDU) (“Produção científica brasileira relacionada à pesquisa sobre a pandemia de COVID-19”, <https://doi.org/10.25824/redu/YLKODL>, Repositório de Dados de Pesquisa da Unicamp, DRAFT VERSION, UNF:6:SxWtwuwTL8DPGIIzd4/JDg== [fileUNF]

Our dataset includes text documents that describe and show the data's trajectory. For this article, the document titles explaining the data are identified with the initials “STI”. Additionally, in conducting the research, analyses were performed using SQL and Python through the Integrated Development Environment (IDE) of Google Colaboratory. The codes used are publicly available via GitHub (<https://github.com/projetodiaspora/STI.git>), aiming to promote transparency and reproducibility of the results.

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Author contributions

Ana Maria Carneiro was responsible for funding acquisition, conceptualizing and designing the methodology, supervising the research process, and contributing to the original draft and subsequent review and editing phases.

Ana Maria Nunes Gimenez worked on conceptualizing and selecting appropriate literature and contributed to writing the original draft and the subsequent revisions.

César Antonio Pereira was responsible for formal analysis and supported the development of the methodology and manuscript review.

Flávia Sayane Silva Meireles was responsible for data curation, methodology, and writing the original draft.

Renata Romolo Brito was responsible for data collection, writing – review and editing.

Clara Harumi Sakuda Tatsugawa was responsible for data collection.

Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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